

Development of Organic Fertilizer and Compost Bin for Home Gardening

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Abstract— India is the second largest manufacturer of fruits and vegetables within the world that amounts to 15 percent of the world's produce. The Central Institute of Post-Harvest Engineering and Technology (CIPHET) Ludhiana, estimated that about 18 percent of the produce is wasted due to poor management. These fruit and vegetable wastes contain significant amount of bio-active compounds that are dumped into the landfills. The aim of this study is to make composting easier that is suitable for households, where mitigation of these fruits and vegetable wastes can be curbed. A compost bin (Nutrition Composter) was designed keeping in thought for home composting that is easy to operate and does not attract pests, flies and odor. Alongside the Nutrition Composter, compost recipe was formulated using fruits and vegetable peels, for herbs and succulents that would provide balanced nutrition through home composting. Home composting method is the most recent strategy that reduces the amount of biodegradable wastes from being sent to the landfill sites. Many local councils in the recent years have strongly promoted home composting and recruitment which is quite significant. Utilization of nutrients from fruit and vegetable wastes have drawn a lot of attention from authors and scientist all over the globe.

Index Terms— Composting, Fruit and Vegetable wastes, Nutrition Composter.

I. INTRODUCTION

India is a global agriculture power houses. ASSOCHAM (2013) mentioned in a study that India incurs post-harvest fruit and vegetable losses worth over Rs, 2 lakhs due to improper food handling and lack of cold storage facilities. It is observed that India generates roughly about fifty-five million tons of fruit and vegetable wastes are dumped at landfills and water bodies. World Bank estimates that between the year 2009 to 2030, food demands will increase by five hundredth as the population grows. Unfortunately, not all food produced will find its way to the tables. It was further reported 44 percent of the food made is wasted, in which out of that, 40 percent is owed to fruit and vegetables.

In accordance to FAO (2007), fruit and vegetable wastes can be accessed in two ways (i) quantitative and (ii) qualitative. Here quantitative refers to the amount or mass which has a diverse effect the food availability for consumption. On the other hand, qualitative refers to the nutritional and caloric value of bioactive compounds, yet they are classified under discarded food item. Most fruits and vegetables are consumed for their flesh or pulp whereas the rest of the fruit such as seeds and; peels are discarded which contains significant amounts of phytochemicals.

Abundant of apple peel waste is produced from apple sauce canned and dried apple industry; A study conducted by Lata and Tomala (YEAR) found that apple peel contains higher amount of flavonols, ascorbate and total phenolic, and thus addition of innovative technology can help produce value added products from these waste. These wastes are glorious

sources of pigments, phenolic compounds, sugar derivatives, organic acids and minerals. (Divina, 2016) mentioned that an efficient way of minimizing waste problems is identifying and recovering bioactive properties from fruit wastes for both

plants and animals. And when it could be re-purposed for agricultural plant crops, they will not be categorized as fruit waste but a means of simply enhancing the quality at a relatively lower cost.

Several studies reported that fruit wastes can benefit plants by promoting its growth and development by enhancing soil fertility and enriching soil microbiota, and protecting them from insects, nematodes, fungi and other plant pathogens. It is a common practice to use fruit peels for composting for fertilizers and this practice if proven to be appropriate by many researches (Tsay et al. 2004; Mercy, 2014).

Different formulations of organic fertilizers with fruit peels enhanced soil fertility and increase the volume and diversity of soil of microorganisms favoring good plant growth. Soil mineral content is increased because fruit peels and wastes contain potassium and minerals essential for plant growth. Pomegranates, orange, sweet lime, banana peels incorporation in soil enhance the number of microorganisms two folds and can be formulated into fertilizers (Chutua et al. 2009; Siskoa et al. 2014).

A. Advantages of Composting

The recent increased interest in composting has arisen as a result of the requirement for environmentally sound waste treatment technologies. Composting is seen as an environmentally acceptable methodology of waste. The process destroys pathogens, converts N from unstable ammonia to stable organic forms, reduces the volume of waste and improves the overall character of wastes. Adding compost to garden also helps to neutralize hydrogen ion concentration and improve the ion exchange capability (CEC) of soils, increasing their ability to hold nutrients for plant use. Compost improves soil structure and boosts nutrient content. With the introduction of organic matter, heavy soils area unit higher equipped to hold water and resist compaction – reducing erosion and runoff.

Recent research additionally suggests that adding compost

to sandy soils will increase wet dispersion by permitting water to move laterally from its purpose of application. As the rate of composting increases it eventually decreases the amount of wastes sent to the landfill for disposal which is essential for low and middle financial gain countries as composting is done at minimal cost.

Composting also enhances the utilization and burning operations by removing organic matter from the waste stream. It also promotes environmentally sound practices, such as the reduction of methane generation at landfills and eventually will scale back the transportation necessities to the landfills. It can be started with a very little capital and operative prices.

B. Disadvantages of Composting

The nutrient value of compost is low compared with that of chemical fertilizers, and the rate of nutrient release is slow and might not typically meet the nutrient demand of crops during a short time, thus ensuing in some nutrient deficiency. The nutrient composition of compost is highly variable compared to chemical fertilizers. Agricultural users have issues concerning levels of serious metals and different doable contaminants in compost, particularly mixed municipal solid wastes. The potential for contamination becomes and vital issue once compost is employed on food crops.

A vast majority of materials are available that are compostable such as pig manure, cattle dung, cow dung, waste from kitchen (fruit, vegetable scraps, egg shells), lawn clippings, tree and shrub leaves, wood shavings, edible oil and fat, animal's shear. The quantity of the materials added is not monitored or weighed out, nor the amount of nutrients present in them are taken into consideration especially during home composting. Hence the amount of nutrients present in the compost is unknown or in rare cases can only be guessed. Whereas the inorganic fertilizers come with exact and precise amount of nutrients contained in them. These organic compos with non-uniform waste added are if unknown nutrients and fail to meet the needs of plants. Hence, in most cases organic fertilizers are often added mixed with chemical fertilizers to provide proper nutrients.

C. Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium requirement by different plants.

According to The Green Pages, France while choosing fertilizers it is very important to check the availability of N: P: K ratio in accordance to the plants you want to fertilize. The following are the main N:P:K ratio used by gardeners

Nitrogen (N) is an element of the chlorophyll in plants, thus giving plants the wealthy inexperienced colour characteristic of a healthy plant. Nitrogen promotes juiciness in forage crops and foliate vegetables.

Phosphorus (P) is necessary for the hardy growth of the plant and activity of the cells. It encourages root development and by hastening the maturity of the plant, it increases the magnitude relation of grain to straw, as well because the total yield. It plays a vital half in increasing the taste property of plants and stimulates the formation of fats, convertible starches and healthy seed.

Potassium (K) in plant nutrition enhances malady resistance by strengthen stalks and stems. It activates various accelerator systems inside plants. Potassium contributes to a thicker cuticle that guards against malady and water loss. It controls the turgor pressure inside plants to forestall

weakening. Potassium enhances fruit size, flavour texture and development and it is involved within the production of amino acids, chlorophyll formation, starch formation, and sugar transport from leaves to roots.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

A. Raw materials, Fruit peels and Vegetable wastes.

The Nutrition Composter was made using Rectangular plastic containers (9x6x8 inches), pen knives, plastic rod, plastic slide (0.5mm).

The biological materials used were categories into two, (i) organic wastesthat were used to make the compost included apple peels, banana peels, orange peels, cucumber peels, papaya peels, tea and coffee grounds which were collected from local vendors and (ii) Succulents like Graptoveria (family Crassulaceae) and Escheveria (family Crassulaceae) were made to order owing to be 6 weeks old. Herbs such as Thai basil and Spearmint were also made on special order owing to b 6 weeks old respectively.

For the study of chemical fertilizer, the control(positive group) was treated with commercial fertilizer Ivzhivyuan granular NPK in the ratio of 20:20:20. The testing of the soil in the later part was carried out by using Hannah Soil Test kit for N:P:K (Nitrogen, Phosphorous, Potassium), manufactured by Hannah instruments Inc. Woonsocket , USA.

B. Design of Nutrition Composter

Figure 1: (a) represents a diagrammatic representation of the Nutrition Composter, stating the three channels. The red slide on the top left represents a removable slide, bottom left rod represents he turner. (b) is the actual picture of the compost bin that was built for this study.

The compost bin was designed such as they contained 3 sections (levels) within one unit. It contains a turner on the rear side of the compost bin which has to be manuallyoperated. The outer coat is made by wrapping and sealing it with cling wrap and a layer of masking tape and painted with black acrylic paint to provide insulation for maintaining the temperature while the compost matures. A see through slide is provided at the back of the compost bin so as to monitor the compost. The sections were created to add the organic waste in the first section, which after a week will be pushed into the second section and similarly will be introduced to the third section where the compost matures for 15 days. The divider is not functional when the first batch of waste is added initially. When the first batch of waste is inoculated from the first to the second chamber, it directly falls into the third chamber, hence it remains in that section for 27 days. Whereas when the second batch of waste is added the divider then acts to differentiate between the second andthird section. After these 3 stages, fresh and matured compost is ready to be used.

C. Preparation of Compost

The compost formula was formulated especially for the two plant species namely herbs and succulents. Formula for herbs labelled as A1 and two formulae for succulents labelled as B1, B2. They were calculated based on their N:P:K adopted from U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) database.

Table I: Proximate composition of compost formulae A1, B1, B2

Compost	Components	Peels/Waste	Weight in grams	Ratio
A1	N	Tea ground	20	20:0:0
	P	Banana peels	10	0:10:0
	K	Papaya peels	250	0:0:10
B1	N	Coffee ground	50	10:0:0
	P	Papaya peels	500	0:20:0
	K	Apple peels	160	0:0:20
B2	N	Coffee ground	500	10:0:0
	P	Banana peels	50	0:20:0
	K	Cucumber peels	30	0:0:20

Fruit peels such of banana, apple, cucumber/ papaya, were used for composting, which were decided on the nutrient component given by USDA of the peels and the ease of availability. Tea and coffee grounds were used as the brown matter for composting. The compost formula was designed on the basis of N:P:K ratio. Nitrogen contributes to promoting leaf growth, Phosphorous provides root, flower and fruit development and Potassium for stem, root growth and protein analysis. The formula for Herbs was designed as such to have higher amount of N, compared to P, K as herbs being more responsive to light in turn need more photosynthesis. Compost for succulents B1, B2 was formulated as such that it incorporates higher requirement of P and K owing to storing water in stem and a flowering plant. These fruit and vegetable wastes were added in the Nutrition Composter, which matured after 30 days and was then tested on herbs and succulents respectively.

D. Experimental setup for testing plants

Here two plant species, herbs and succulents were used for testing. The experimental plants were categorized into three main groups; (i) treatment, (ii) positive control (treated with commercial/chemical fertilizer) and (iii) negative control (tap water). 5 seedlings of Thai basil and Spearmint each were administered under treatment, positive and negative control groups. 5 seedlings each of Graptoveria and Escheveria were used for treatment of B1, B2, positive and negative control respectively.

The setting was optimized such that the temperature was maintained around 25-27°C and white fluorescent light was subjected on these seedlings. The seedlings under compost treatment were allocated in the first level of the growth chamber, followed by the seedlings under chemical fertilizer and the last level was allocated to the seedlings under no fertilizer for herbs and succulents respectively. Equal light was provided to seedlings under different treatment. The watering of herbs was carried out every second day for herbs and once a week for succulents whereas and fertilizing the herbs were once a week and as that of the succulents it was done once a month. Plant Growth parameters.

Data was collected based on the growth rate of compost formula, chemical fertilizer and no fertilizer. The data collected includes plant height, number of leaves and

flowerings. They were measured once in every week. Plant height was measured in cms. Number of leaves and flowerings were noted by counting each leaf and flowerings.

E. Chemical Test for pH and N:P:K.

Testing for N:P:K and pH was carried out using Hannah Soil Test kit.

F. Statistical analysis.

The statistical analysis for the study was carried out using Microsoft Excel version 2016 on Windows 2010. The average was calculated and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and independent t-test were used to determine the significant difference between the height, no. of flowerings, no. of leaves amongst seedling under different treatments and controls.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Compost

Three types of composts that were carried out for Compost A1 for herbs, B1, B2 for succulents.

Fig 2: (a) shows compost A1 for herbs, while diagram (b) and (c) show compost of B1 and B2 for succulents. The pictures were taken after 30 days of composting

B. Herbs treated with compost A1, chemical fertilizer and no fertilizer.

Thai basil and Spearmint showed a relatively positive response on being treated with compost A1 on comparison to the chemical fertilizer and no fertilization. Owing to plant height, seedlings treated with A1 compost showed an increment in height, Thai basil being 13.4±1.2 cm and Spearmint being 13.3±1.6 cm that might be due to the increase of nutrient availability.

Figure 3: The effect of compost A1, chemical fertilizer, and no fertilizer (a) height of plant, (b) number of leaves of herbs (c) number of flowerings

The number of leaves recorded the highest in seedling treated by chemical fertilizer owing to 50 ± 11.7 . The fact that A1 compost as well as chemical compost contained the same amount of N, on the later part the seedlings treated with chemical fertilizer withered away due to accumulation of chemical.

Whereas, seedlings treated with A1 compost showed a steady growth Thai basil bearing 38 ± 2.1 leaves and spearmint bearing 33 ± 7.5 .

Potassium is an essential nutrient that plays an important role in flowering. Compost A1 contained the quantity of K on comparison to N and P. In the early stage of development all the nutrients are used up in the development of roots and leaves and after a good development period flowerings are then produced. The highest number of flowers were borne by seedlings treated with compost A1, whereas seedlings treated with chemical fertilizer withered and seedling with no fertilizer showed no major increment in height, leaves and eventually no flowering.

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B. Succulents treated with compost B1, B2, chemical fertilizer and No fertilizer.

Testing compost B1 and B2 on 6 weeks old Grapitoveria and Escheveria, were evaluated only on the basis of sustainability and perishability.

Compost B1 and B2 was formulated so as to contain double amount of P compared to N. Succulents are drought tolerant which means they tend to have the ability to store water during the times of draught. Thus they have large root system and stem structure. Phosphorous is essential for promoting stem, root growth and protein thus compost B1 and B2 contain double amount of Phosphorous as compared to N.

Compost B1 and B2 contain a total N: P: K of 10:20:20 whereas the chemical fertilizer contains 20:20:20. Both Grapitoveria and Escheveria showed positive effect compost B1 and B2 until week 11 and could not sustain during week 12 right up to week 15. With regards to seedlings treated with chemical fertilizer perished away after week 6 of fertilization.

Moreover the chances of over fertilization is high in potted plants. However, the seedlings under no fertilizer perished right away as 6 week old seedlings are separated from the parent plant and no nutrients were supplied to them, as all means of nutrients were blocked they perished sooner.

C. Chemical testing on Soil for N:P:K and pH.

The chemical test for soil was carried after a period of 3 months of fertilization with compost as well as chemical fertilizer to ensure the amounts of N, P, K intended to provided has been met. Compost recipe A1 was formulated in the ratio 20:10:10 which means double the amount of N compared to P and K. The result of Hannah N, P, K soil test suggest that the traces on N in the soil was medium for N and low for P and K. The residue of N after being utilized by the plant is medium. Compost B1 and B2 was formulated owing to 10:20:20, double the amounts of P and K compared hence the N, P, K remains in the soil treated with compost B1 and B2 shows low remains of N and medium for P and K. As these macronutrients added to the soil are in the form of organic matter it is stored longer and decomposes as organic matter while becoming more available to plant over time. Chemical fertilizer having the composition of 20:20:20 showed high amounts of N, P, K, thus having higher amounts of N, P, K in the soil, Thus leading to over excess build up and accumulation of inorganic fertilizers which withers the plant and eventually kills the plant.

pH of the soil poses as an important factor as it influences a variety of activities. The optimum pH is between 6.0 and 7.5 for most bacteria. Ph between 5.5 and 8.0 is even suitable for fungi and actinomycete activity. Stability of compost is also determined by pH range, if the pH falls between 5.5 to 8.0 indicates the compost stability and photo toxicity. Compost formula A1, B1 and B2 all three fall under pH 6 which shows that they fulfil the requirement of being an optimum medium for bacterial and fungal activities as well as it is stable for fertilizing plants. According to M.H Dyer in SF GATE the optimum pH for Thai basil and Spearmint is 5.5 to 6.0 which is achieved in the compost formula A1. Succulents have a requirement of pH between 5.5 to 7.0 which is achieved in both B1 and B2 compost. Whereas in the chemical fertilizer the pH observed was 5 which doesn't meet the requirement for both herbs as well as succulents.

Statistical analysis was done using one-way ANOVA on average between the seedlings treated with compost (A1, B1 and B2), chemical fertilizer and no fertilizer. In the output the P-value for this statistics on Thai basil- height is 5.91×10^{-5} , number of leaves is 1.44×10^{-7} and number of flowerings is

6.87x10⁻⁷ as seen in Table 4.8, whereas in Spearmint- height the value of P observed in Table 4.9 is 0.066671, for number of leaves the value of P as seen is 1.92x10⁻⁸ and number of flowerings, the P value is 9.69x10⁻¹. All the above mentioned values, P < 0.001 which means that there was significant difference in the plant height, number of flowers and leaves amongst seedlings treated with compost A1, B1 and B2.

In sum and substance, the height, number of leaves and flowerings were recorded on weekly basis and cumulative height, number of leaves and flowerings were plotted against the respective week. It was observed that the highest number of height was observed to be 13.4 in Thai basil and 13.3 in Spearmint and both were treated with compost A1, while the lowest plant height was in Thai basil was 3.3cm and in Spearmint was 3.3cm both under negative control group, which were not treated with any fertilizer. Hence it is observed that the compost formulated for herbs and succulents gave better growth in Thai basil and Spearmint when compared to chemical fertilizer and no fertilizer. In terms of number of leaves, the maximum yield was 50 in Thai basil, treated with chemical fertilizer and in Spearmint was 33 which was treated with compost A1. The highest number of flowerings achieved in Thai basil and Spearmint were 4 and 6 respectively, both were treated with compost A1.

However, the N: P: K test kit used for this study only gives the result of the quantity of N, P, K in terms of trace, low, medium and high which only gives an estimation of quantity of N, P, K and not the exact amount present. The succulent seedlings used to test for compost B1 and B2 should have been kept under longer time for observation as they take time to grow which was not achieved in this study due to time constraints.

CONCLUSION

The main objective of this study was building a compost bin with guidelines on how to use it to compost fertilizer for herbs and succulents. This was well established by developing a 30-day compost plan using fruit and vegetable peels formulated for herbs and succulents. As these compost formula A1, B1 and B2 were specially designed using fruits, vegetable peels along with tea and coffee grounds as brown matter, during the composting process it did not produce any foul odor nor did it attract any kind of flies or fleas. The second objective of this study focuses on measuring growth parameters towards the compost formulated for herbs and succulents which was developed using the compost bin. Thai basil and Spearmint showed a positive growth response towards the compost formulated; Whereas succulents didn't show a positive response for the compost formulated for them respectively.

However, the N:P:K test kit used for this study only obtained in the terms of trace, low, medium and high which only gives the estimated quantity. The compost formulated for succulents wasn't efficient to get positive results. For future recommendations, wet lab test can be employed for quantification of N,P,K and the Nutrition composter could be advanced with features such as built in thermometer, periodic and automated turning of the compost and insulated coating material for maintaining high temperature within.

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